

Synthesis of 3,4'-Dimethyl-6-ethyl-7',8'-furocoumarin

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Furocoumarins can be synthesised from coumarones by building a pyrone ring¹ or from coumarins by building a furane ring² on them. A synthesis of a furocoumarin from 4-methyl-6-ethyl-8-acetylbumbelliferone has been described in this communication.

The sodium salt of 4-methyl-6-ethyl-8-acetylbumbelliferone (I) was condensed with bromo-acetic ester. The reaction mass was hydrolysed when an oxy-acid, 4-methyl-6-ethyl-7-(carboxymethoxy)-8-acetylcoumarin (II), was formed. This was heated with acetic anhydride and sodium acetate when a compound having a composition $C_{15}H_{14}O_5$ (i.e. less by CH_2O_2 than that of the acid) was formed. Carbon dioxide was observed to have been given off during heating and a molecule of water must have been lost during ring-closure. The cyclised compound was therefore formulated as 3,4'-dimethyl-6'-ethyl-7',8'-furocoumarin (III).

4-Methyl-6-ethyl-8-acetyl-7-(carboxymethoxy)-coumarin (II).—The dry sodium salt of 4-methyl-6-ethyl-8-acetylbumbelliferone (I, 7 g.) was heated with bromo-acetic ester (26ml) for 1 hr. at 160-70°. The ester formed was gently boiled with NaOH solution (10 ml) for 15 min., cooled, and acidified. The resulting precipitate was extracted with bicarbonate solution. The extract after filtration was acidified. The resulting acid was crystallised from 20% ethanol. (Found: C, 62.69; H, 5.10. $C_{16}H_{16}O_6$ requires C, 63.16; H, 5.26%).

1. Limaye and Sathe, *Rasayanam*, 1937, 1, 87.

2. Limaye, *Ber*, 1932, 65, 375; *Rasayanam*, 1936, 1, 1; 1939, 187; Shah and Shah, *this Journal*, 1940, 17, 41.

3,4'-Dimethyl-6'-ethyl-7',8'-furocoumarin (III).—The coumarin (II, 2g.), fused sodium acetate (6 g.), and acetic anhydride (20 ml) were heated at 150-55° for $\frac{1}{2}$ hr. Carbon dioxide evolved during heating. The reaction mass was poured over crushed ice. The resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol, m. p. 157°, yield 1.5 g. (Found: C, 74.8; H, 5.89. $C_{13}H_{14}O_3$ requires C, 74.39; H, 5.79%).

Sincere thanks of the author are due to Dr. R. C. Shah for his kind help.

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Received March 11, 1964.